

A Robust Decentralised Strategy for Multi-Task Control of Unmanned Aerial Systems. Application on Underactuated Aerial Manipulator

J.Á. Acosta, C.R. de Cos and A. Ollero

Abstract—These days we demand Unmanned Aerial Systems (UASs) fly autonomously and be able to physically interact with their environment executing prescribed tasks. An excellent example of that are the Aerial Manipulators (AMs) i.e. UASs formed by the join of an Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) and a Robot Manipulator (RM). Moreover, the lack of structured workspaces in outdoor operations is challenging for the control system, forcing to increase notably its complexity to meet such requirements but keeping in mind the trade-off between the task performance and computational burden. In this work, a nonlinear control strategy is proposed and thoroughly tested on an AM. The strategy combines the use of robust controllers separately for both UAV and RM exploiting their stability margins to optimise different prescribed criteria in real time. The inclusion of this optimisation in the loop shows excellent results, sharing priorities of the controllers as required. Following this idea, two different strategies have been tested in a benchmark system showing promising results and, furthermore, feasible for a subsequent implementation in the available platform.

I. INTRODUCTION

The control of Unmanned Aerial Systems (UASs) is an emerging topic. The complexity and capabilities of these systems are growing fast and hence demanding increasingly complicated control systems. Moreover, we do not only demand that UASs fly autonomously, but also physically interact with the environment executing prescribed tasks. A good example of that are Aerial Manipulators (AMs) in the field of Robotics, which are flying machines formed by the join of an Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) and a Robot Manipulator (RM) (see [1], [2], [3], [4], [5] and [6]). In fact, those interaction capabilities were demonstrated under the ARCAS project [7], that supported partially this work and it has been a cutting-edge framework for the design and development of a cooperating free-flying robot system for assembly and structure construction. The complexity of the available AM (Fig. 1), consisting of an octoquad ([8], [9]) mounting a Robai Cyton Gamma 1500 7-DoF lightweight manipulator [10] with a smart built-in Dynamixel position-control servos [11] and controlled by a real-time operating system QNX Neutrino [12], is currently being considerably increased in the current AEROARMS project [13].

Let us enumerate some examples of the current functionalities of aerial robots and unmanned aerial systems: joint transportation of loads as in [14], [15], collaborative tasks in [16], [17], grabbing objects with an UAV during flight in [18], [19], [3], mobile ground platforms [20], [21], underwater vehicles [22] and space robots [23]. There have

Fig. 1. Available UAS: quadrotor plus 7-link manipulator.

also been developments focused on objects perching on rods or beams to allow UAVs to increase their endurance in missions as in [24] and [18].

From the control point of view, AMs are a special class of underactuated mechanical systems, and so they inherit all their properties, being instrumental to understand their dynamics and coupling effects in order to design efficient controllers. Dynamics of different UAVs are thoroughly described in [25], [26] and of RMs in [27] and references therein. On the one hand, several control strategies have been already reported for UAVs: tracking and stabilisation in [26] and [28]; a backstepping approach in [29] and with robust adaptation in [30]; by means of optical flow in [31]; using Hamiltonian framework in [32]; and employing widely used strategies based on the linearisation and time-scale separation in [26], [33] and [34]. Moreover, a robust controller of an AM has already been reported by some of the authors in [35], for a simplified version of the available experimental platform of Fig. 1, based on the Interconnection and Damping Assignment Passivity-Based Control (IDA-PBC) methodology. On the other hand, in the field of RMs there is a great variety of available numerical control algorithms, such as the Closed-Loop Inverse Control Kinematic (CLICK) of first-order in [27], [36], [37], [38], [39], [40] and of second-order in [36], [41], [42]. Nevertheless, even though CLICK methods provide good performances, the lack of common structured spaces in outdoor aerial manipulation is highly demanding for the control algorithms and some robustness properties are needed to cope with “random” cartesian end-effector trajectories during flight. Thus, in [43] some of the authors enhanced those algorithms adding and formalising an integral error action, improving properties as zero steady-state tracking error, rejection of constant disturbances and a smoother behaviour, all strongly needed for the execution of smart manipulation tasks.

Furthermore, in the control system design of AMs, it is generally accepted that both UAV and RM operations are considered as disturbances to each other, reinforcing the need of robust methods. In this work, we go a step forward in the control design, taking the advantages of the stability margins obtained with those actual decentralised robust controllers but incorporating a strategy that combines both–aerial vehicle and manipulator–algorithms via the optimisation of shared subordinate tasks. Thus, the paper is structured as follows: Section II describes the general framework; in Section III the strategy combining both algorithms is thoroughly described; Section IV is devoted to the benchmark application, whose simulation results are presented in Section V. Finally, the paper is wrapped up with a conclusion section.

Notation: All vectors are *column* vectors. When clear from the context the subindex of the operator ∇ and the arguments of the functions will be omitted. The form $\|\cdot\|_{\Gamma}$ denotes the Euclidean norm weighted by matrix Γ .

II. BACKGROUND AND FRAMEWORK

The dynamics of UASs, and in particular for AMs, can be described by means of the Lagrange equations [44], [45]. Thus, denoting by $(q, \dot{q}) \in \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^n$ the generalised coordinates and velocities, their dynamics become

$$\Sigma(\ddot{q}, \dot{q}, q) = u + u_{ext} \quad (1)$$

where $\Sigma(\ddot{q}, \dot{q}, q) := M(q)\ddot{q} + C(q, \dot{q})\dot{q} + \nabla V(q)$, with $M(q) \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ the symmetric and positive definite inertia matrix, $V(q) \in \mathbb{R}$ the potential function, the matrix $C(q, \dot{q}) \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ containing the Coriolis and centrifugal forces and u_{ext} shaping the effects of external generalised forces, like friction and drag forces. In the case of a quadrotor, the generalised input vector $u \in \mathbb{R}^m$ reads

$$u = G(q) \cdot F, \text{ with } G(q) \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times m}, m := 4 + n,$$

and $F = [T, \tau]^T$, with $T \in \mathbb{R}^4$ the thrust forces given by the rotors and $\tau \in \mathbb{R}^n$ the joint torques of the RM. Alternatively, this control problem is naturally formulated in cartesian space which, away from singularities¹, has a fully equivalent formulation to that of the joint space (1) through the analytic jacobian matrix, namely $J(q)$, which is straightforward assuming its inverse mapping [27].

As it was thoroughly discussed in [35], the closed-loop stability analysis becomes very involved because of the mechanical underactuation of AMs inherited from the UAV dynamics (see [25], [26]), whereas RMs are fully-actuated. In fact, this added complexity demands an exhaustive analysis in both cases free $u_{ext} = 0$ and constrained motion $u_{ext} \neq 0$, becoming apparent that underactuated mechanical systems cannot be commanded to follow arbitrary trajectories.

Finally, let us remind that the potential energy function of UAS is not lower bounded (see example in [35]) and hence, the addition of damping does force the UAS to lose potential but without resting anywhere. This fact provides to the UAS

¹Singularities are state-space points where the jacobian lacks rank.

Fig. 2. Control strategy of the multi-task UAS control.

with a cyclo-passivity property [46] instead of the stronger passivity one, i.e. no equilibrium exists while “un-powered”.

III. MULTI-TASK NONLINEAR CONTROL STRATEGY

In this section, we thoroughly describe the nonlinear control strategy designed for the UAS. With the help of the sketch illustrated in Fig. 2 the whole strategy can be easily summarised as follows:

- 1) Describe the interconnection between the UAV and the k^{th} mission system dynamics involved through a “succinct feature”, namely π_k^d . In our case of study, we have chosen the RM torque transmitted to the UAV.
- 2) The UAV controller is designed with a reduced-order model that takes into account that feature π_k^d . Moreover, this controller has to be robust to the uncertainty introduced by the order reduction.
- 3) The optimiser, characterised by the cost functional Ψ_k , “reshapes” the demand π_k^d from the UAV to render π_k^* instead, according to an interconnection criterion (e.g. increasing the torque transferred to the UAV to cope with a contour condition for the RM).
- 4) Design the mission control to track the modified request π_k^* , in particular the RM controller.
- 5) The control loop is closed when the UAV receives $\tilde{\pi}_k$, which is the actual value of the “succinct feature” through the inherent dynamic coupling.

From a control point of view, the above presented control algorithm requires some specific attributes for the different subsystems. On the one hand, the UAV controller needs disturbance rejection capabilities to deal with the differences between the reduced-order and full dynamics, and also with the mismatch between the demanded π_k^d and the actual $\tilde{\pi}_k$. On the other hand, the mission controller needs good tracking capabilities to follow π_k^* and low sensitivity to numerical errors. Finally, in between, the optimiser needs to be defined through bounded operators and computable in finite time.

As it is intentionally shown in Fig. 2, the strategy has to be nonlinear. To understand why, let us briefly show how difficult –even impossible– it would be to complete a suitable design with classical linear control theory. Thus, for the UAV controller, a standard one-degree of freedom design would not be enough because it needs to follow two objectives at different frequency ranges. Thereupon, at

least a two-degree of freedom design would be needed. On the contrary, a linear design could work for the mission control depending on the subsystem considered. In the case of the RM, the nonlinear nature of the direct kinematic makes it quite difficult, but for example a LPV designed in different operation points might work. However, let assume that around an operating point and flight envelope, a linear design for both controllers works reasonably well. Some factors, as the unexpected external disturbances and the own nonlinear nature of the optimisation criteria, make very difficult to shape the frequency characteristic to cover a wide range of operating points and regimes.

In what follows in this section, we summarise the controllers used for the available UAS based on previous author's works. The stability and convergence properties of the whole control strategy are in [47] that it will be reported elsewhere. The full scheme of the control system is provided in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Full control system scheme.

A. Passivity-based control of the UAV via IDA-PBC

In this section we briefly describe the robust passivity-based controller obtained in [35]. Roughly speaking IDA-PBC is an energy-shaping methodology providing a generalised port-controlled Hamiltonian structure in closed loop, i.e. with a physical structure. This methodology is stated in Hamiltonian framework, however it is fully equivalent to the Lagrangian one (see [48] and [49]). As it was thoroughly described in [35], IDA-PBC was introduced in [50] to regulate underactuated mechanical systems as

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{q} \\ \dot{p} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & I_n \\ -I_n & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \nabla_q H \\ \nabla_p H \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ G(q) \end{bmatrix} F, \quad (2)$$

where $q \in \mathbb{R}^n$, $p \in \mathbb{R}^n$ are the generalised position and momenta, respectively, $F \in \mathbb{R}^m$ and $G(q) \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times m}$ with rank $m < n$, and a full-rank left annihilator $G^\perp(q) \in \mathbb{R}^{(n-m) \times n}$, i.e. $G^\perp G = 0$ and rank $n - m$, and where $H(q, p) = 1/2 p^\top M^{-1}(q) p + V(q)$ is the total energy with $M(q) = M(q)^\top > 0$ the inertia matrix, and $V(q)$ the potential energy. The main result is that for all matrices $M_d(q) = M_d^\top(q) \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ and functions $V_d(q)$ that satisfy some Partial Differential Equations (PDEs) (see [51] for details), and for some $J_2(q, p) = -J_2^\top(q, p) \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, then

the system (2) in closed-loop with $F = \hat{F}(q, p)$ given by

$$\hat{F} = G^\dagger (\nabla_q H - M_d M^{-1} \nabla_q H_d + J_2 \nabla_p H_d) - K_v \nabla_p H_d, \quad (3)$$

with $G^\dagger = (G^\top G)^{-1} G^\top$, takes the Hamiltonian form

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{q} \\ \dot{p} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & M^{-1} M_d \\ -M_d M^{-1} & J_2 - G K_v G^\top \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \nabla_q H_d \\ \nabla_p H_d \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

with $K_v = K_v^\top > 0$ and closed-loop energy function as

$$H_d(q, p) = \frac{1}{2} p^\top M_d^{-1}(q) p + V_d(q). \quad (5)$$

Additionally, if M_d is positive definite in a neighborhood of $q_* \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and $q_* = \arg \min V_d(q)$, then $(q_*, 0)$ is a stable equilibrium point of (4) with Lyapunov function (5). This equilibrium is asymptotically stable if it is locally detectable from the output $G^\top \nabla_p H_d$. We refer the interested readers to [51] and [52] for a compact derivation of the PDEs. It is noticeable the closed form for J_2 made in [51] and given by

$$J_2 = \sum_{i=1}^{n_o} p^\top M_d^{-1} \alpha_i W_i, \quad n_o := \frac{n}{2}(n-1).$$

Let us summarise the robust controller for the UAS considering the longitudinal dynamics of a quadrotor plus n -link manipulator given in [35]. The reduced-order nonlinear model, proposed by some of the authors there, has shown a good trade-off of both robustness and computational burden. As it has been aforementioned this reduced-order model keeps a succinct feature of the RM to describe the influence of its movement without needing a complete dynamical description. The chosen feature is the distance of the centre of gravity of the robot with respect to the base of the aerial vehicle, called $L(t) = \overline{PB}$ (see Fig. 4), such that whenever the manipulator rests at any position $\dot{L}(t) = 0$ and $\ddot{L}(t) \neq 0$, otherwise, $t \geq 0$. Notice that, although the model has been reduced, it still captures the essence of being underactuated. In [35] we show that, unfortunately, the control law with the directly measurable coordinates is not computable and so, we provided a new set of coordinates to do so, whose existence is explained in [35] and based on [52].

Fig. 4. Sketch of longitudinal dynamics of the UAS.

Thus, consider the longitudinal dynamics of the AM (Quadrotor + RM), as depicted in Fig. 4, where the dynamics

of the n -link manipulator is described only by its centre of gravity. To be consistent with [35] we keep the notation \bar{q} , instead of q , for that new set of coordinates. Thus, let $\bar{q} \in \mathbb{R}^4$ be the generalised coordinates defined as (see Fig. 4): \bar{q}_1 and \bar{q}_2 the horizontal and vertical positions of the centre of gravity of the whole system (CG), respectively; \bar{q}_3 is the pitch quadrotor angle and \bar{q}_4 is the pitch angle of the (CG) frame both with respect to the inertial reference frame (N). Finally, three active forces and moments are defined: the two thrusters (T_1 and T_2) and the manipulator resultant torque acting on the quadrotor (τ) together with its reaction on the manipulator. The latter is the aforementioned interconnection needed between both subsystems, i.e. $\pi^d = \tau$ of Fig. 2. Thus, the force vector is $F = [T_1 \ T_2 \ \tau]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^3$. We keep here only the necessary relations and parameters of the model, referring to the interested reader to [35] for a complete description of the dynamics. Thus, the set of coordinates selected are directly related with the key parameter L as

$$(kL_{CG}(\bar{q}))^2 := d^2 + L^2 + 2dL \cos \left\{ \arctan \left(\frac{s_{(3-4)}}{\delta(\bar{q})} \right) \right\}$$

where we defined $\delta(\bar{q}) := d/L - c_{(3-4)}$ and $s_{(a-b)} := \sin(\bar{q}_a - \bar{q}_b)$ and $c_{(a-b)} := \cos(\bar{q}_a - \bar{q}_b)$. The remaining parameters are: m_Q and m_B the quadrotor and manipulator masses at positions Q and B , respectively; I_{22} the inertia of the whole robot manipulator at Q and $k := 1 + m_Q/m_B$. The underactuation can be seen from the left-hand kernel (nullspace) of G which is spanned by $G^\perp = [c_3, -s_3, 0, 0]$. The result of [35] is summarised in the following proposition.

Proposition 1: Consider the dynamics of the AM in \bar{q} -coordinates. Then, the static state-feedback (3) ensures:

- (i) A closed-loop port controlled Hamiltonian dynamics with dissipation of the form (4) defined by: the desired inertia matrix as

$$M_d(\bar{q}) = k \begin{bmatrix} m_B & 0 & m_{13}/k & 0 \\ 0 & m_B & 0 & 0 \\ m_{13}/k & 0 & I_{22}/k & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & m_Q L_{CG}(\bar{q})^2 \end{bmatrix};$$

with m_{13} a tuning gain; the potential energy as

$$V_d(\bar{q}) = -gk m_B \frac{I_{22}}{m_{13}} \ln(\cos \bar{q}_3) + \Phi(\cdot);$$

where $\Phi(\bar{q}_2 - \frac{I_{22}}{m_{13}} \ln(\cos \bar{q}_3), \bar{q}_3 - \frac{m_{13}}{I_{22}} \bar{q}_1, \bar{q}_4)$, is a free function of its arguments; and the interconnection matrix elements as J_2^{ij} , $i, j = 1, \dots, 4$, all zero except

$$J_2^{14} = -\frac{m_{13} p_4}{I_{22} L_{CG}(\bar{q}_3, \bar{q}_4)} \frac{\partial L_{CG}(\bar{q})}{\partial \bar{q}_3}.$$

- (ii) $(\bar{q}_{1*}, \bar{q}_{2*}, 0, \bar{q}_{4*}, 0, 0, 0)$ is a (locally) stable equilibrium with Lyapunov function (5), for any constants $0 < m_{13} < \sqrt{k m_B I_{22}}$ and $k_i > 0$, $i = 1, 2, 3$.
(iii) For L , \dot{L} and $\ddot{L} \in \mathcal{L}_\infty$, in particular let $|L| < B_1^2$ and $|\dot{L}| < B_2^2$, with $B_1, B_2 > 0$, all the trajectories are bounded in $(\bar{q}, p) \subseteq \mathbb{R}^2 \times (-\pi/2, \pi/2) \times \mathbb{R}^5$ and satisfy

$$G(\bar{q}(t))^\top \nabla_p H_d(\bar{q}(t), p(t)) \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } t \rightarrow \infty,$$

if the control gain K_v satisfies $K_v > k_v I_3 > 0$ with

$$k_v > \sqrt{\frac{m_Q}{2}} \frac{1 + 2l_T^2}{l_T} B_1 B_2.$$

Remark 1: The closed-loop potential energy function is defined through the free function Φ with the only requirement of $H_d > 0$, and in [35] it was chosen to be quadratic.

Remark 2: In [35] the nonlinear controller was designed with the RM resting at a fixed position and then, we proved the robustness of that controller whenever the movements of the manipulator remain bounded—as it is standard in normal tasks. In Proposition 1 both results have been summarised. For those who are not familiar with control theory, the crucial difference between both cases is that the former closed-loop dynamics is autonomous and the latter non-autonomous. Thus, whenever $\dot{L}(t) = 0$ the desired equilibrium is asymptotically stable, unlike for $\dot{L}(t) \neq 0$ that uniform stability of the equilibrium is preserved. The latter means that for any initial condition all the trajectories converge to the positive limit set $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \dot{H}_d(t) = 0$, which is a subset of $\dot{H}_d(t) \equiv 0$, $t \geq 0$, containing the desired equilibrium. For that latter case, we highlight that even though uniform asymptotic stability remains still unproven, the strong property of uniform stability is guaranteed, providing the closed-loop system, among others, with the ability to withstand disturbances.

B. Inverse kinematic control of the robot manipulator

In this section we describe briefly the robust controller provided in [43], where a robust redesign of the known CLIK algorithm has been formulated and solved. Thus, let n and l be the joint space and cartesian task space dimensions, respectively. Thus, End-Effector (EE) cartesian velocity vector $v_E \in \mathbb{R}^l$ is defined as $v_E := [\dot{x}, \omega]^\top$, where \dot{x} represents the linear velocity vector and ω are its angular rate, both in EE frame with respect to base frame. The desired velocities are defined as $v_E^* = [\dot{x}^*, \omega^*]^\top$. Let $\mathbf{J} \in \mathbb{R}^{l \times n}$ denote the geometric jacobian and $\dot{\gamma} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ the joint angles vector, so that the direct kinematics equation for a general manipulator is governed by $v_E = \mathbf{J} \dot{\gamma}$ (see [27], [53], [54]). The inverse kinematics for this redundant manipulator can be formulated as a (local) constrained linear optimisation problem. Thus, for a given EE velocity v_E and a jacobian \mathbf{J} we look for a solution on $\dot{\gamma}$ as a result of the optimisation problem subject to the constraint $v_E = \mathbf{J} \dot{\gamma}$ and defined by the quadratic cost functional on joint velocities given by $\Psi(\gamma, \dot{\gamma}) := \frac{1}{2} \|\dot{\gamma}\|_\Gamma^2$, with $\dot{\gamma} := \dot{\gamma} - \dot{\gamma}_0$ and with $\dot{\gamma}_0$ being the homogeneous solution and $\Gamma \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ a positive definite weighting matrix. Necessary condition for optimality yields

$$\dot{\gamma} = \mathbf{J}^\dagger v_E + (I_n - \mathbf{J}^\dagger \mathbf{J}) \dot{\gamma}_0. \quad (6)$$

Notice that by choosing $\Gamma = I_n$ then \mathbf{J}^\dagger becomes the standard *pseudoinverse* (see [27] for details). The above optimisation strategy to control a general manipulator (6) was refined in [43] adding robustness through an integral action. Among others, the achieved robustness allowed us to use the modified algorithm onboard in AMs. In fact, a critical issue solved by the modified algorithm was the sensitivity to numerical errors—critical onboard—involving,

among others, drift phenomena which, in turn, cause a mismatch in the EE pose. Moreover, the non-uniqueness of standard angular representation, as the Euler angles, becomes also a drawback for numerical algorithms, and the use of unit quaternions for the orientation is an efficient way to overcome it (see [55]). Thus, let $\text{col}(\sigma_0, \sigma) \in \mathbb{R}^4$ denote a quaternion with $\sigma_0 \in \mathbb{R}$ and $\sigma \in \mathbb{R}^3$ its scalar and vector components, respectively. The cartesian error vector becomes

$$e := \begin{bmatrix} e_p \\ e_o \end{bmatrix} := \begin{bmatrix} x_e^* - x_e \\ \Delta\sigma \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^l, \quad (7)$$

where e_p and e_o are the position and orientation error, respectively (see [43] for details), and $\Delta\sigma = \sigma_0\sigma_d - \sigma_{0_d}\sigma - S(\sigma_d)\sigma$ where S is the skew-symmetric cross-product matrix (see [55], [56] and [57]). In the following proposition we summarise the result obtained in [43].

Proposition 2: Let $\zeta \in \mathbb{R}^l$ be defined as $\dot{\zeta} := e$ and assume $\det(\mathbf{J}\mathbf{J}^\top) \neq 0$. The control algorithm given by

$$\dot{\gamma} = \mathbf{J}^\dagger (v_E^* + \epsilon K^2 \zeta + Ke) + (I_n - \mathbf{J}^\dagger \mathbf{J}) \dot{\gamma}_0, \quad (8)$$

where $K := \text{diag}(K_p, K_o)$ with K_p, K_o positive definite and diagonal matrices and $\epsilon := \text{diag}(\epsilon_p I_3, \epsilon_o I_3)$ for $\epsilon_p, \epsilon_o \in (0, 1]$, ensures (global) exponential stability of $e = 0$ (7).

Remark 3: Notice that, the already known first-order CLIK algorithm is a particular case for $\epsilon_p = \epsilon_o = 0$ of the extended algorithm provided (see [27], [36]).

The stability result of Proposition 2 relies on the assumption of a full-rank jacobian in the whole work space, i.e. stay away from singularities. The so-called Damped Least Squares (DLS) *inverse* allows to overcome this problem with a good trade-off between large joint velocities and cartesian task accuracy as shown in [41], [58], [36] or [59]. The DLS algorithm is a modified *inverse* as a result of a relaxed optimisation problem of (6) defined by the cost function as

$$\Psi(\gamma, \dot{\gamma}) := \frac{1}{2} \|\dot{\gamma}\|_\Gamma^2 + \frac{1}{2} \|v_E - \mathbf{J}\dot{\gamma}\|^2, \quad (9)$$

such that the damped version of (8) becomes

$$\dot{\gamma} = \mathbf{J}^\dagger_{DLS} (v_E^* + \epsilon K^2 \zeta + Ke) + (I_n - \mathbf{J}^\dagger_{DLS} \mathbf{J}) \dot{\gamma}_0.$$

C. Optimiser

The optimisation criteria have been included through the *pseudoinverse* of the inverse kinematic controller. For this, two strategies have been explored and, although they seem equivalent there are some qualitative differences. The first one posed in cartesian space (as in [43]), and the second one posed in the joint space. Both have in common the interconnection term to be optimised, which recall that is the desired torque, namely τ_d . The functional (9) is redefined in each case to fulfil the interconnection requirement. According to the notation in Fig. 2, $\pi^* = \tau^*$ where τ^* is the objective torque that the RM controller will track, which is the torque exerted by the whole RM at the base of the UAV.

Cartesian-space controller

The first controller proposed, depicted in Fig. 5, is that of Proposition 2 applied to AMs, in which the objective function has been modified to take into account the desired torque τ_d expected by the UAV. Additionally, the relaxed

Fig. 5. Cartesian-space control algorithm.

formulation of the optimisation problem provides a way to take into account the inertial weighted damping term in order to minimise the perturbations due to high accelerations in the first joint, whose inertial effects are more relevant than those closer to the EE. This results in the following cost functional

$$\Psi_C(\gamma, \dot{\gamma}, \ddot{\gamma}) := \frac{1}{2} (\alpha_{ID} \|\dot{\gamma}\|_{\tilde{W}}^2 + \|v_E - \mathbf{J}\dot{\gamma}\|^2 + \alpha_{\tau_d} \rho(\tilde{\tau}))$$

with $\tilde{\tau} := \tau_d - \tau^*$ and where the two first terms are those of original damped pseudo-inverse (9) and enhanced by the normalising diagonal matrix \tilde{W} of the RM inertia sub-matrix; the last term corresponds to the extra optimisation criterion to comply with the UAV demand with a normalising function $\rho \in \mathbb{R}_+$. Finally, α_{τ_d} and α_{ID} are constants defined on $[0, 1)$. This results in the following *pseudoinverse* as

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\gamma} &= \Lambda^\dagger \left(\alpha_{ID} \tilde{W} P \dot{\gamma}_0 + \mathbf{J}_\gamma^\top (v_E - \mathbf{J}_\xi \dot{\xi}) - \alpha_{\tau_d} \rho' \tau_1^* \right) \\ \Lambda &:= \alpha_{ID} \tilde{W} + \mathbf{J}_\gamma^\top \mathbf{J}_\gamma - \alpha_{\tau_d} \rho' \tau_2^* \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

where we have split the jacobian into $v_E = \mathbf{J}_\gamma \dot{\gamma} - \mathbf{J}_\xi \dot{\xi}$, the joint configuration of the RM and position of the UAV, respectively, and $\tau_1^* := \partial \tau^* / \partial \dot{\gamma}|_{\dot{\gamma}=0}$ and $\tau_2^* := \partial^2 \tau^* / \partial \dot{\gamma}^2$.

Joint-space controller

Fig. 6. Joint-space control algorithm.

This controller is based on splitting the torque in its static and dynamic terms and minimise them independently as shown in Fig. 6. The static error is minimised with an inverse kinematic algorithm formulated in γ and subject to the constraint $x_E(\gamma) = x_E^*$, rendering a joint reference over time for the algorithm of the dynamic term. Thus, the cost functional is defined as

$$\Psi_{REF}(\gamma) := \frac{1}{2} (\tau_d - \nabla_{\theta_0} V)^2, \text{ s.t. } x_E(\gamma) = x_E^*. \quad (11)$$

On the other hand, the dynamic error is faced with a pure joint-space controller whose target is the dynamic reference and with cost functional defined as

$$\Psi_L(\gamma, \dot{\gamma}, \ddot{\gamma}) := \frac{1}{2} ((\dot{\gamma} - \dot{\gamma}_e)^2 + \mu_{ID} \|\dot{\gamma}\|_{\tilde{W}}^2 + \mu_{\tau_d} (\tilde{\tau}^*)^2),$$

with $\tilde{\tau}^* := \tau_d - \frac{1}{2} \|\dot{\gamma}\|_{\tau_2^*}^2 - \tau_1^* \dot{\gamma}$, $\mu_{ID}, \mu_{\tau_d} \in [0, 1]$ and \tilde{W} being the same weighting matrix defined in the previous controller. Notice that γ is now limited to the previous configuration (11) in order to avoid drastic reference changes. The purpose of this controller is to provide a smooth trajectory to the reference that minimises the possible interferences produced in the torque dynamic terms. Altogether, results in

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\gamma} &= \Lambda^\dagger \left(\dot{\gamma}_e - \frac{1}{2} \mu_{\tau_d} \tau_1^* \right), \\ \Lambda &:= I_{4 \times 4} + \mu_{ID} \tilde{W} + \mu_{\tau_d} \tau_2^*. \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

In summary, this controller is robust to the steady torque terms but with a limited response to the RM accelerations.

IV. BENCHMARK APPLICATION

In order to validate the control strategies presented above, all the simulations are based on a model for the longitudinal dynamics of an AM, consisting of an UAV with a four-link planar RM connected to the UAV with an offset from the centre of mass of the vehicle (Fig. 7), whose parameters are presented in Table I. The generalised coordinates of the UAS

Fig. 7. Benchmark UAS sketch.

from (1) are $q = (\xi, \gamma)^\top \in \mathbb{R}^3 \times \mathbb{R}^4$, i.e. $\mathbf{l} = 3$ and $\mathbf{n} = 4$, with $\xi = (x, y, \theta_0)^\top$ and $\gamma = (\theta_1, \theta_2, \theta_3, \theta_4)^\top$ being the position of the UAV and RM configuration, respectively (see also [27] and [60]). The UAV parameters according to Propo-

TABLE I
MODEL PARAMETERS

Masses[kg]		Lengths[m]			Inertias[kg · m ²]	
m_{UAV}	m	l_T	l	d	I_{UAV}	I_L
2	0.15	0.3	0.2	0.1	$7 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$5 \cdot 10^{-4}$

sition 1 are $m_B = 4m$, $m_Q = m_{UAV}$, and $I_{22} = M_{33}^{RM}(q)$. The inertia matrix of the AM $M(q) = M^{UAV} + M^{RM}$ is composed by those of the UAV and the RM, assembled

through their elemental jacobians associated with translations and revolutions, subindexes t and r respectively, as

$$\begin{aligned} M^{UAV} &= m_{UAV} \left(J_t^Q \right)^\top J_t^Q + I_{UAV} \left(J_r^Q \right)^\top J_r^Q, \\ M^{RM}(q) &= m \sum_{i=1}^4 \left(J_t^i \right)^\top J_t^i + I_L \sum_{i=1}^4 \left(J_r^i \right)^\top J_r^i. \end{aligned}$$

Notice that both M^{UAV} and $M^{RM,rev}$ are matrices of constant terms, where the superscript *rev* stands for revolute. The form of the inertia sub-matrices results in a Coriolis matrix where Christoffel symbols read

$$c_{ijk} = \frac{m}{2} \left(b_{ij,k}^{RM,t} + b_{ik,j}^{RM,t} - b_{jk,i}^{RM,t} \right),$$

with terms $b_{ij,1}^t, b_{ij,2}^t, b_{11,k}^t, b_{12,k}^t, b_{22,k}^t, b_{77,k}^t$ zero $\forall i, j, k$.

To connect both UAV and RM controllers it is essential to accurately estimate the link torque transmitted by the manipulator to the vehicle. Recall that it is used to minimise the difference between the actual physical value and the UAV controller demanded one. Its approximation is obtained using a concept similar to the structural sub-matrices static reduction [61], considering the dynamic equations without the friction and the drag terms (1). Thus, neglecting translational coupling terms the approximation for this torque becomes

$$\tau^* = M_{0\gamma}(\gamma) \ddot{\gamma} + \frac{1}{2} \theta_0^T \bar{C}_{0\gamma}^0(\gamma) \dot{\gamma} + \frac{1}{2} \|\dot{\gamma}\|_{\bar{C}_{0\gamma}^0(\gamma)}^2 + \nabla_{\theta_0} V \quad (13)$$

and defining $K_1 := 2c_{343}(\gamma)$, $K_2 := 2c_{353}(\gamma)$, $K_3 := 2c_{363}(\gamma)$ and $K_4 := 2c_{373}(\gamma)$, the Coriolis-related matrices become $\bar{C}_{0\gamma}^0(\gamma) = (K_1, K_2, K_3, K_4)$ and $\bar{C}_{0\gamma}^\gamma(\gamma)$ accordingly. We underscore that the simple form of the Coriolis-related matrix drastically reduces the computational load.

V. SIMULATION RESULTS

Simulations to validate the proposed control strategies have been carried out in a more realistic simulator including dynamic friction and aerodynamic drag forces through u_{ext} in (1), but without considering the EE orientation. For both cartesian and joint space controllers, two different approaching conditions have been simulated for a fair comparison (see Table II). In the first one, the UAV target position is above the objective and the manipulator's perturbation on the UAV is not so important. In the second one, the approaching configuration is less favourable for the interaction.

Cartesian-space controller

This control has been implemented with a smooth transition between the flight phase, in which the manipulator is retracted, and the approaching one. This can be clearly seen in the smoothness of the EE trajectory in Fig. 8. Furthermore, it is noticeable that this performance produces an approaching phase with substantially higher impact on the whole operation (Fig. 9), introducing a perturbation in the UAV trajectory and steady error in its position.

TABLE II
SIMULATION CONDITIONS

INITIAL CONDITIONS						
UAV position and pitch [m,rad]			RM configuration [rad]			
x	y	θ_0	θ_1	θ_2	θ_3	θ_4
0	0	0	-0.4	0.5	1.6	2
UAV speeds [m/s,rad/s]			RM angular speeds [rad/s]			
\dot{x}	\dot{y}	$\dot{\theta}_0$	$\dot{\theta}_1$	$\dot{\theta}_2$	$\dot{\theta}_3$	$\dot{\theta}_4$
0	0	0	0	0	0	0
TARGET CONDITIONS						
UAV [m,rad]			RM [m]			
Normal approach		x	y	θ_0	x	y
		-3.8	5	0	-3	5
Hard approach		x	y	θ_0	x	y
		-3.5	4.6	0	-3	5
CONTROL GAINS						
k_1	k_2	k_3	α_{ID}	α_{τ_d}	μ_{ID}	μ_{τ_d}
50	8	10	0.5	0.1	0.35	0.75

Fig. 8. Flight phase of the Cartesian-space controller.

Fig. 9. Approaching phase of the cartesian-space controller.

1) *Simulation I. Normal approach:* In this first simulation, both UAV and EE positions show a smooth convergence, mainly due to an exponential transition added, to trigger the integral CLICK algorithm (Fig. 10). Moreover, the torque in this case (Fig. 11) has been well counteracted despite of the approaching phase has started with the RM deployed (Fig. 10 at 10s). That initial configuration for the approaching phase forced a demand of negative pitching moment (Fig. 11) from the UAV controller, but the arm position was incompatible with such demand. Finally, the thrusts of both rotors have converged to an almost symmetrical condition without noticeable vibrations or noise.

Fig. 10. Simulation I. Position and speed of the UAV and the manipulator.

Fig. 11. Simulation I. Control characteristics and end-effector position.

2) *Simulation II. Hard approach:* While in the previous simulation the transient between both phases have been smooth, for a harder approaching condition the UAV presents a slight deviation when deploying the manipulator that causes significant vibrations (Fig. 12), especially in the angular speeds of the manipulator. However, the EE converges to the target with minimal vertical error as the thrusts of the rotors counterbalance the torque produced by the manipulator configuration (Fig. 13). In summary, this control strategy tolerates hard conditions without experiencing significant negative results. This robustness is provided by the multi-task controller introduced, which is capable of modifying the UAV target to achieve a successful operation.

Fig. 12. Simulation II. Position and speed of the UAV and the manipulator.

Fig. 13. Simulation II. Control characteristics and end-effector position.

Joint-space controller

In comparison with the cartesian-space control algorithm, this solution presents a clear multi-phase operation (Fig. 14), given by a longer unperturbed flight and a shorter and more abrupt approaching phase (Fig. 15).

Fig. 14. Flight phase of the joint-space controller.

3) *Simulation III. Normal approach:* While in the previous simulations both UAV and EE converge smoothly to the final target, in this case there is a significant change of the reference for both controllers once the manipulator starts

Fig. 15. Approaching phase of the joint-space controller.

the approaching phase (Fig. 16 and 17). Additionally, this solution presents smoother variations in the configuration angles of the RM (Fig. 16), filtering the angular speed ripple during the approaching phase. However, it also produces a

Fig. 16. Simulation III. Position and speed of the UAV and the manipulator.

peak of UAV speed just after the RM is deployed, which is counterbalanced by the UAV controller without introducing notable steady error in position. It is remarkable that the joint-space controller presents significant noise in both thrust and desired link torque (Fig. 17). Nevertheless, this situation only produces vibrations of the EE around the target position. These vibrations do not affect notably the stability of the UAV, as it can be seen in the behaviour of the distance to the manipulator centre of mass.

4) *Simulation IV. Hard approach:* In this badly-conditioned approaching simulation, the solution presents a similar general behaviour than the previous one. However, although in the preceding conditions the UAV speed after the deployment of the RM did not affect its convergence, in this simulation the oscillation is maintained longer (Fig. 18). Furthermore, this perturbation produces a reduction of the distance to the manipulator centre of mass and a noticeable imbalance of the rotor thrusts to compensate the pitch moment peak (Fig. 19).

Remark 4: It is worth to comment that other sub-tasks using the homogeneous solution (see [62], [27]) and the Saturation in the Null Space (SNS) of [63] and [64] have not been explored yet in this work for AMs. In [43] they

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work has been supported by the AEROARMS project that receives funding from the European Unions Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 644271, and by the AEROMAIN national project under grant DPI2014-59383-C2-1-R.

REFERENCES

- [1] I. Maza, F. Caballero, J. Capitán, J.R. Martínez, and A. Ollero, "A distributed architecture for a robotic platform with aerial sensor transportation and self-deployment capabilities," *Journal of Field Robotics*, vol. 28, no. 3, pp. 303–328, 2011.
- [2] A. Albers, S. Trautmann, T. Howard, T.A. Nguyen, M. Frietsch, and C. Sauter, "Semiautonomous flying robot for physical interaction with environment," *Robotics, Automation and Mechatronics*, 2010.
- [3] V. Ghadiok, J. Goldin, and W. Ren, "Autonomous indoor aerial gripping using a quadrotor," *IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems*, pp. 4645–4651, 2011.
- [4] I. Maza, J. Kondak, M. Bernard, and A. Ollero, "Multi-UAV cooperation and control for load transportation and deployment," *Journal of Intelligent and Robotics Systems*, vol. 57, no. 1, pp. 417–449, 2010.
- [5] N. Michael, J. Fink, and V. Kumar, "Cooperative manipulation and transportation with aerial robots," *Autonomous robots. Special issue: Robotics: Science and Systems*, vol. 30, pp. 73–86, 2011.
- [6] C. Korpela, T. Danko, and P. Oh, "MM-UAV: Mobile manipulating unmanned aerial vehicle," *Journal of Intelligent and Robotics Systems*, vol. 65, no. 1, pp. 93–101, 2012.
- [7] ARCAS project, "Aerial Robotics Cooperative Assembly System," in <http://www.arcas-project.eu/>, European Commission under the Seventh Framework Programme (FP7/2007-2013 ICT-2011-287617).
- [8] G. Heredia, A.E. Jiménez-Cano, M.I. Sánchez, D. Llorente, V. Vega, J. Braga, J.Á. Acosta, and A. Ollero, "Control of a multirotor outdoor aerial manipulator," in *IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems*, Dpto. de Ingeniería de Sistemas y Automática, Universidad de Sevilla, Sevilla, Spain, September 2014, IEEE.
- [9] A.E. Jiménez-Cano, J. Martín, G. Heredia, R. Cano, and A. Ollero, "Control of an aerial robot with multi-link arm for assembly tasks," in *IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation*, Dpto. de Ingeniería de Sistemas y Automática, Universidad de Sevilla, Sevilla, Spain, May 2013, IEEE.
- [10] "Robai Cyton Gamma 1500," <http://robai.com/robots/gamma-1500/>.
- [11] "Dynamixel - Robotis," http://www.robotis.com/xe/dynamixel_en.
- [12] "QNX Neutrino RTOS," <http://www.qnx.com/products/neutrino-rtos/neutrino-rtos.html>.
- [13] AEROARMS project, "Aerial Robotic system integrating multiple ARMS and advanced manipulation capabilities for inspection and maintenance," in <http://www.aeroarms-project.eu/>, European Commission under the H2020 Framework Programme.
- [14] M. Bernard, K. Kondak, I. Maza, and A. Ollero, "Autonomous transportation and deployment with aerial robots for search and rescue missions," *Journal of Field Robotics*, vol. 28, no. 6, pp. 914–931, 2011.
- [15] I. Maza, F. Caballero, J. Capitán, J.R. Martínez de Dios, and A. Ollero, "A Distributed Architecture for a Robotic Platform with Aerial Sensor Transportation and Self-Deployment Capabilities," *Journal of Field Robotics*, vol. 28, no. 3, pp. 303–328, May 2011.
- [16] I. Maza, J. Kondak, M. Bernard, and A. Ollero, "Multi-UAV cooperation and control for load transportation and deployment," *Journal of Intelligent and Robotics Systems*, vol. 57, no. 1, pp. 417–449, 2010.
- [17] N. Michael, J. Fink, and V. Kumar, "Cooperative manipulation and transportation with aerial robots," *Autonomous robots. Special issue: Robotics: Science and Systems*, vol. 30, pp. 73–86, 2011.
- [18] D. Mellinger, Q. Lindsey, M. Shomin, and V. Kumar, "Design, modelling, estimation and control for aerial grasping and manipulation," in *IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems*, San Francisco, CA, 2011, pp. 2668–2673.
- [19] P. Pounds, D. Bersak, and A. Dollar, "Grasping from the air: Hovering capture and load stability," in *IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation*, Shanghai, CN, 2011, pp. 2491–2498.

Fig. 17. Simulation III. Control characteristics and end-effector position.

Fig. 18. Simulation IV. Position and speed of the UAV and the manipulator.

Fig. 19. Simulation IV. Control characteristics and end-effector position.

were only tested for the robot manipulator.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this work, a nonlinear strategy to control UASs is proposed, which combines decentralised robust controllers and an optimiser that manages their stability margins in real time, under some prescribed criteria according to the application. The optimisation idea has shown excellent results being able to comply with both demands sharing their priorities. Two different strategies following the same idea have been thoroughly tested in a benchmark UAS consisting in an UAV and a RM. Both strategies have shown good but different performances as the priority is shared in different ways.

- [20] Y. Yamamoto and X. Yun, "Coordinating locomotion and manipulation of a mobile manipulator," *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control*, vol. 39, no. 6, pp. 1326–1332, 1994.
- [21] C. Korpela, T. Danko, and P. Oh, "MM-UAV: Mobile manipulating unmanned aerial vehicle," *Journal of Intelligent and Robotics Systems*, vol. 65, no. 1, pp. 93–101, 2012.
- [22] G. Antonelli, *Underwater Robotics. Motion and Force Control of Vehicle-Manipulator Systems*, vol. 2 of *Springer Tracts in Advanced Robotics*, Berlin Heidelberg, Springer-Verlag (D), 2006.
- [23] K. Yoshida and B. Wilcox, *Space robots and systems*, pp. 1031–1063, Springer Handbook of Robotics. Springer, b. siciliano and o. khatib edition, 2008.
- [24] A. Albers, S. Trautmann, T. Howard, T.A. Nguyen, M. Frietsch, and C. Sauter, "Semi-autonomous flying robot for physical interaction with environment," *Robotics, Automation and Mechatronics*, 2010.
- [25] T. Cheviron, A. Chriette, and F. Plestan, "Generic nonlinear model of reduced scale UAVs," in *IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation*, Kobe, J, 2009, pp. 3271–3276.
- [26] K. Nonami, F. Kendoul, S. Suzuki, W. Wang, and D. Nakazawa, *Autonomous Flying Robots. Unmanned Aerial Vehicles and Micro Aerial Vehicles*, Springer, 2010.
- [27] B. Siciliano, L. Sciacivco, L. Villani, and G. Oriolo, *Robotics. Modelling, planning and control*, Springer-Verlag (UK), 2009.
- [28] P. Castillo, R. Lozano, and A. Dzul, "Stabilization of a mini rotorcraft with four rotors," *IEEE Control Systems Magazine*, vol. 25, no. 6, pp. 45–55, 2005.
- [29] T. Madani and A. Benallegue, "Sliding mode observer and backstepping control for a quadrotor unmanned aerial vehicles," in *American Control Conference*, New York City, NY, 2007, pp. 5887–5892.
- [30] F. Gavilan, R. Vazquez, and J.Á. Acosta, "Adaptive control for aircraft longitudinal dynamics with thrust saturation," *Journal of Guidance, Control, and Dynamics*, vol. 38, no. 4, pp. 651–661, 2015.
- [31] V. Lippiello, G. Loianno, and B. Siciliano, "MAV indoor navigation based on a closed-form solution for absolute scale velocity estimation using optical flow and inertial data," in *IEEE Conference on Decision Control and European Control Conference*, 2011, pp. 3566–3571.
- [32] R. Mahony, S. Stramigioli, and J. Trumpf, "Vision based control of aerial robotic vehicles using the port Hamiltonian framework," in *IEEE Conference on Decision Control and European Control Conference*, Orlando, FL, 2011, pp. 3526–3532.
- [33] R. Mahony and T. Hamel, "Robust trajectory tracking for a scale model autonomous helicopter," *International Journal of Robust and Nonlinear Control*, vol. 14, no. 12, pp. 1035–1059, 2004.
- [34] P. Pounds and A. Dollar, "UAV rotorcraft in compliant contact: Stability analysis and simulation," in *IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems*, San Francisco, CA, 2011, pp. 2660–2667.
- [35] J.Á. Acosta, M. I. Sánchez, and A. Ollero, "Robust Control of Underactuated Aerial Manipulators via IDA-PBC," in *Decision and Control (CDC), 2014 IEEE 53rd Annual Conference on*, Los Angeles, California, USA, Dec. 15–17 2014, IEEE, pp. 673–678.
- [36] S. Chiaverini, G. Oriolo, and I. Walker, "Kinematically redundant manipulators," in *Handbook of Robotics*, pp. 245–268. Springer, Berlin Heidelberg, 2008.
- [37] P. Falco and C. Natale, "On the Stability of Closed-Loop Inverse Kinematics Algorithms for Redundant Robots," *IEEE Transactions in Robotics*, vol. 27, no. 4, pp. 780–784, August 2011.
- [38] H. Das, J. Slotine, and T. Sheridan, "Inverse kinematic algorithms for redundant systems," *IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation*, pp. 43–48, 1988.
- [39] G. Antonelli, S. Chiaverini, and G. Fusco, "A New On-Line Algorithm for Inverse Kinematics of Robot Manipulators Ensuring Path Tracking Capability Under Joint Limits," *IEEE Transactions on Robotics and Automation*, vol. 19, no. 1, pp. 162–166, February 2003.
- [40] L. Sciacivco and B. Siciliano, "Coordinate transformation: A solution algorithm for one class of robots," *IEEE Trans. Syst., Man, Cybern.*, vol. SMC-16, no. 4, pp. 550–559, 1986.
- [41] F. Caccavale, S. Chiaverini, and B. Siciliano, "Second-order kinematic control of robot manipulators with jacobian damped leastsquares inverse: Theory and experiments," in *IEEE/ASME Transactions on Mechatronics*, Dipartimento di Informatica e Sistemistica, Università degli Studi di Napoli Federico II, Naples, Italy, September 1997, IEEE.
- [42] A. De Luca, G. Oriolo, and B. Siciliano, "Robot redundancy resolution at the acceleration level," *Laboratory Robotics and Automation*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 97–106, 1992.
- [43] M. I. Sánchez, J.Á. Acosta, and A. Ollero, "Integral action in first-order Closed-Loop Inverse Kinematics. Application to aerial manipulators," in *Robotics and Automation (ICRA), 2015 IEEE International Conference on*, May. 26–30 2015, pp. 5297–5302.
- [44] V. Lippiello and F. Ruggiero, "Cartesian Impedance Control of a UAV with a Robotic Arm," in *10th IFAC Symposium on Robot Control International Federation of Automatic Control*, Dubrovnik, Croatia, September 5–7 2012, pp. 704–709.
- [45] V. Lippiello and F. Ruggiero, "Exploiting Redundancy in Cartesian Impedance Control of UAVs Equipped with a Robotic Arm," in *IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems*, Vilamoura, Algarve, Portugal, October 7–12 2012, pp. 3768–3773.
- [46] J. C. Willems, "Dissipative dynamical systems Part I: General Theory," *Arch Rational Mech. Anal.*, vol. 45, no. 5, pp. 321–351, 1972.
- [47] J.Á. Acosta, C.R. de Cos, and A. Ollero, "Finite-time Computable Nonlinear Control for Unmanned Aerial Robotics," Preprint, 2016.
- [48] G. Blankenstein, R. Ortega, and A.J. van der Schaft, "The matching conditions of controlled Lagrangians and interconnection assignment passivity based control," *International Journal of Control*, vol. 75, no. 9, pp. 645–665, 2002.
- [49] D.E. Chang, A.M. Bloch, N.E. Leonard, J.E. Marsden, and C.A. Woolsey, "The equivalence of controlled lagrangian and controlled hamiltonian systems for simple mechanical systems," *ESAIM: Control, Optimisation, and Calculus of Variations*, vol. 8, pp. 393–422, 2002.
- [50] R. Ortega, M. Spong, F. Gomez, and G. Blankenstein, "Stabilization of underactuated mechanical systems via interconnection and damping assignment," *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control*, vol. 47, no. 8, pp. 1218–1233, 2002.
- [51] J.Á. Acosta, R. Ortega, A. Astolfi, and A. M. Mahindrakar, "Interconnection and damping assignment passivity-based control of mechanical systems with underactuation degree one," *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control*, vol. 50, no. 12, pp. 1936–1955, 2005.
- [52] G. Viola, R. Ortega, R. Banavar, J.Á. Acosta, and A. Astolfi, "Total Energy Shaping Control of Mechanical Systems: Simplifying the Matching Equations Via Coordinate Changes," *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control*, vol. 52, no. 6, pp. 1093–1099, 2007.
- [53] A. Ollero, *Robótica: manipuladores y robots móviles*, Marcombo, 2001.
- [54] J.J. Craig, *Introduction to Robotics: Mechanics & Control*, Addison-Wesley Publ., 1986.
- [55] K.W. Spring, "Euler Parameters and the Use of Quaternion Algebra in the Manipulation of Finite Rotations: A Review," *Mechanism and Machine Theory*, vol. 21, no. 5, pp. 365–373, 1986.
- [56] B.P. Ickes, "A New Method for Performing Digital Control System Attitude Computations using Quaternions," *American Institute Aeronautics and Astronautics Journal*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 13–17, January 1970.
- [57] J. H. Conway and D. A. Smith, *On Quaternions and Octonions: Their Geometry, Arithmetic, and Symmetry*, Ak Peters Series. Taylor & Francis, 2003.
- [58] S. Chiaverini, "Singularity-robust task-priority redundancy resolution for real-time kinematic control of robot manipulators," *IEEE Transactions in Robotics and Automation*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 398–410, June 1997.
- [59] A. Deo and D. Walker, "Overview of Damped Least-Squares Methods for Inverse Kinematics of Robot Manipulators," *Journal of Intelligent and Robotic Systems*, , no. 14, pp. 43–68, 1995.
- [60] L.R.G. Carrillo, A.E.D. López, R. Lozano, and C. Pégard, *Quad Rotorcraft Control: Vision-Based Hovering and Navigation*, Springer Science & Bussines Media, 2012.
- [61] M. Paz and W. Leigh, *Integrated Matrix Analysis of Structures. Theory and Computation*, Springer US, 2001.
- [62] A. De Luca and G. Oriolo, "The reduced gradient method for solving redundancy in robot arms," *Robotersysteme*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 117–122, 1991.
- [63] F. Flacco, A. De Luca, and O. Khatib, "Motion Control of Redundant Robots under Joint Constraints: Saturation in the Null Space," in *IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation*, RiverCentre, Saint Paul, Minnesota, USA, May 2012, IEEE.
- [64] F. Flacco and A. De Luca, "Optimal redundancy resolution with task scaling under hard bounds in the robot joint space," in *IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation*, Karlsruhe, Germany, May 2013, IEEE.